

Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers' Identity and Paradigm Shift in English Language Teaching: Current Trend in Thai Educational Context

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Abstract

English is currently the main means of international communication among people from diverse linguistic backgrounds. Therefore, English language education has played a significant role in all domains of society and connecting people globally. There has been a significant increase in the number of the controversial native/non-native dichotomy in English Language Teaching (ELT). The fallacy that successful communication can always be assured if an individual can approximate to the native speakers' competence has long been prevalent to uphold in English language education in Thailand. This paper aims to criticize the non-native English-speaking teachers' identity in accordance with the dominant native speakers' norms of English in Thailand as well as the use of English teaching paradigm which contradicts the sociolinguistic reality of today's world communication. This paper reconceptualizes the status of Non-Native English Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) through the lens of professional identity and the orientation of English language teaching pedagogy in current trend of Thai educational setting in order to raise educators and scholars' awareness of the importance of international intelligibility rather than linguistic prestige. Additionally, the English teacher identity and paradigm shift in English language teaching in Thailand will be proposed. Such issues will provide a powerful lens to reexamine the value in English language teachers in many dimensions: the requirement through qualifications, students' viewpoints and administrators' perspectives. Hopefully, the critical discussion in the paper would offer the insight into dominant teaching paradigm in Thailand which should be reconsidered to be compatible with global communicative needs, particularly in the era of international communication and ELT.

Introduction

With regard to English language education where English is extensively used as the de facto working language, English language teachers exceptionally play an indispensable role in promoting the effective learning process and enabling students to achieve the ultimate goal in the globalized world of communication (Harmer, 1991). From the past up to the present, the traditional influence of Native English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) is rather evident owing to their so-called superiority in pronunciation and accent, which determines learners' positive judgment and preference towards the NESTs, while NNESTs are considered less competent (Canagarajah, 1999). However, with the sociolinguistic fact where today's English is significantly diverse according to the different natures of the people with different linguistic and sociocultural backgrounds, English has clearly become plural by its own legitimacy (Seidlhofer, 1999). That is, varieties of Englishes are universally accepted as they are successfully employed in different communicative contexts in global communities with or without the presence of the native speaker (Cook, 1999). The acceptance of the World Englishes (WEs) paradigm has therefore fundamentally promoted the critical value of the NNESTs in the modernization and development of English language teaching. In this paper, the issue of NNESTs' identity and their contribution to the change in teaching practices under the notion of world Englishes in the current trend of Thai educational context will be discussed.

Story of NNESTs and NESTs identity: An overview

Admittedly, although the NNESTs have enormously obtained their professional status in English language instruction and research in the past decades, they are not receiving the positive preference as much as their NEST counterparts (Medgyes, 1992; Mahboob, 2010). This popular perception often results from the belief that the NESTs have a great influence in English language education worldwide since they are better target language providers than NNESTs. However, as we can see, a number of NNESTs, nowadays, tend to play a significantly increasing role in fulfilling their own pedagogical implications for regional multilingualism. In other words, they are the ones who can potentially accommodate this world language in the classroom with their teaching

styles and strategies so that English can serve local communicative needs as well as promote local indigenous languages and cultures among the non-native users of English in the region (Kirkpatrick, 2013).

As a result, competent non-native teachers of English are regarded as ones who could enhance the important variables in educational environment. That is, they have a positive, realistic contribution to the students' future use of English within the global and local communities. To describe, they have several special and many bright sides of their English skills, teaching process, and interactive approach. Therefore, it should increase an awareness of the truth that being NNESTs can have the same qualities to be effective language teacher like NESTs. Since non-native teachers of English have struggled with the power of equality in their position between native and non-native speakers in educational institutions (Canagarajah, 1999; Mahboob, 2009), studies on attitudes towards the dichotomy of NESTs vs. NNESTs are one of the noteworthy areas which could reveal and assert their professional qualification. As a response to NNESTs' identity, the two examples of research articles which investigated students' attitudes particularly towards NNESTs in outer and expanding circle settings (Kachru, 1992) in English language education will be discussed to clarify NNESTs' identity, their value and contribution.

The first article was conducted by Ling and Braine (2007) in the outer circle country to examine the attitudes of university students towards their NNESTs in Hong Kong context. They were in an undergraduate level in three years of from seven universities. The findings generally exhibited that students had positive attitudes towards their NNESTs. The answers from the questionnaires revealed that students had no difficulty in learning with NNESTs who had their great attempt to teach their students. The results from the interviews also showed the favorable attitude towards NNESTs. The main reasons were due to their effective pedagogical skills similar to those efficient NESTs. Specifically, NNESTs had the same cultural background as their students in Hong Kong educational context. They could understand the students' particular difficulties and provide effective strategies in learning English. They further stated that NNESTs had effective pedagogical skills and the ability to use students' mother tongue in teaching and in examination-oriented teaching approach. In the same vein, Watson Todd and Pojanapunya (2009) explored the explicit and implicit attitudes towards NESTs and NNESTs of 261 Thai university students at King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi (KMUTT) in Thailand. A set of questionnaires was used to elicit the students' explicit attitudes including preferences and feelings towards NESTs and NNESTs. The use of Implicit Association Test (IAT) was additionally employed to detect their implicit attitudes. The findings revealed that, for explicit attitudes, the students expressed a preference for NESTs over NNESTs. Yet, when tested by IAT in terms of implicit attitudes, they had moderately warmer feelings towards NNESTs than NESTs. This indicated that the students showed no significant preference for NESTs.

These two studies are important in the way that even though there have formerly been some studies revealing that NNESTs themselves are assumed to be inferior and often unconfident in different areas of instructional practices when compared with the NEST counterpart (Macdonald, 2002; Baker, 2014; Levis & Barriuso, 2016), their research findings yielding the similar results in regard to the participants' overall positive attitudes towards NNESTs, therefore, indicate the potential of NNESTs in teaching practices.

As affirmed by Medgyes (1992, 2001) in the seminal study of "native or non-native: Who's worth more?" and "when the teacher is a non-native speaker", the NNESTs can actually be a model for being a better learner. NNESTs can also provide more effective strategies in learning. In addition, as they were in the same position as their students, they can give more information about the English language as well as better anticipate and prevent sensitive language difficulties which tend to occur during the learning process. Last but not least, they can make use of students' first language (L1) in teaching. In teaching practices, according to Levis et al. (2016), even in the area of teaching pronunciation which NNESTs seem to be most reluctant to perform, NNESTs are, in fact, able to enhance learners' English pronunciation effectively. This shows that, like teaching any other skills, successful teaching rather depends on experience, knowledgeable instructional practices, and professionalism than being native or non-native speakers of English. It could reflect the fact that all non-native teachers of English should believe in themselves in teaching practices and to construct positive professional identities with recognizing the existence of the varieties of English on today's world communication, when teaching qualification and professionalism should be considered the most significant determination in successful English language teaching. That is, they are able to enjoy their pride of their identity since they could provide their own language choices as bilingual speakers of English whose teaching could contribute to the international intelligibility. They could also promote the effective learning process and enabling students to achieve the ultimate goal in the globalized world of communication (Harmer, 1991). To illustrate, NNESTs are considered as a profitable source of language diversity, for cross-cultural communication, in order to provide the knowledge of local socio-cultural communities and languages for their students.

Observation and Critical discussion

Looking upon Thai educational context during the past 25 years, the native-speakerism has strongly influenced on Thai curriculum. Specifically speaking, achieving native-like pronunciation has been accepted as an achievable ideal of communicative and pronunciation teaching. In addition, a traditional teaching method has been persistent with the fallacy that if students can approximate to the native-like competence, their learning is regarded successful. This fact currently contradicts with the sociolinguistic reality of the ultimate goal of using English as the main tool in today's world communication which the idea of successful communication is to reach the aim of negotiating meanings. The international intelligibility and language diversity should be primarily realized rather than reserving the notion of one single standard norm of English in the classroom.

NNESTs professional identity in Thai educational context

According to Tajfel (1979), professional identity referred to social recognition as a member of professional community and the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills and the development of new values, attitudes and behaviors. In the aspect of pedagogical context for teaching English as an International language, an exploration of NNESTs' professional identity could lead to a better understanding of the NNESTs' teaching position which is firmly associated with their pedagogical implication. In Mackay's (2002) article, she suggested that in teacher education paradigm in the current era of globalization, teachers should realize the fact of the role of English language as the main medium for English pedagogy. That is to say, they should be aware of the choices of which language to teach and how to promote a variety of English in the classroom to meet their students' need in relation with the adjustment to the local and international contexts. Mackay (2002) also indicates that acceptability of sociolinguistic reality should be highlighted in teaching practices along with equipping students with accommodation skills in using English in the real communicative situation. Besides, teachers should adjust their attitudes to be more open-minded and be more flexible to the realm use of English as today's global language before they implement their knowledge in the classroom. In Thai educational context, native-English speaker teachers has long been received the positive preference as the ideal model teachers due to their better fluent competence and having a native-like pronunciation leading to successful communication. Most recently, a copious number of previous studies have been conducted to question the myth about the NNEST/NEST dichotomy (Canagarajah, 1999; Milambiling, 2000; Liu, 2001; Avasadanond, 2002; Liu & Qiao, 2006; Bernaus & Gardner, 2008; Kara, 2009; Thomson, 2012; Ahmed, 2013; Sit, 2013; Sheikh & Mahmood, 2014). The main argument of this issue to point out that the NNESTs, whom has been claimed as a "deficiency" model could actually create their professional development to effective English language education. To elaborate, NNESTs, in fact, have contributed to the advancement of English through their training, experience, multiple competencies and dedication. Many researches (Brutt-Griffler, 1999; Phillipson, 1996; Matsuda & Matsuda, 2001) unveiled the fact that the question of whether being NNESTs or NESTs are better was not the key point. In particular, what is crucial is that how qualified and expertise a teacher is regardless of being NNESTs or NESTs. According to Wahyudi (2012), Thai educators should shift the focus to the significance of being a professional English teacher and should stress on an individual's professional matters. In addition, NNESTs could be proud of their own identity and professional ability. They can become proficient in English and value their pride of being themselves and with their own pronunciations if it is not an obstacle of international intelligibility. Many Thai English teachers can be equally expressed through their English pronunciations like those of the native speakers'. With hopeful direction, emphasizing true professionalism would better help decrease inequality between NESTs and NNESTs in Thai education setting.

Current situation of Thai English language education

Thai National Education Curriculum, in 2002, carried out the educational reformation to reconstruct English as the forefront of national intellectual development (Bupphanhasamai, 2012). The dramatic demands for English have extensively used owing to the birth of The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) community since not merely has English become a main means of communication amongst the community, but it has also been accepted as an official language. Thus, English influential status has currently pressed Thai government to launch policies on foreign language education by establishing English as a compulsory subject for all schools in the past 10 years. However, the situation of English language teaching in Thailand has long been notorious for being impractical for many decades. This desperate situation is directly due to an over-reliance on examination-oriented backgrounds, especially those in the university admission which does not compatible with the aims of education acts (Canagarajah, 1999) emphasizing on the importance of learning by doing and practicing analytical thinking. Their ultimate goal of studying English is for the sake of reaching high scores by coping with multiple choice examinations. This phenomenon leads to the dismal situation of developing students' communicative proficiency in the real world situation.

In the aspect of current reformation of Thai English language education's planning and policy, its planning and policy do not follow the practical framework of sociolinguistics since it is developed by merely follow Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) in all dimensions including learning, teaching and assessment (Darasawang, 2007; Saengboon, 2002) without reexamining back to the realistic language use in the

local dimension which coincide with Thai communicative setting. As we can see in content of Thai national examination, the part of speaking section of the ordinary national English test (O-NET), for instance, heavily contains a number of idiomatic expressions of specific aspects of native speakers' cultural and social values, particularly British and American standard. These expressions are relatively useless in the real communicative situation since Thai students are not used widely among the vast majority of people from other international communities. To simplify this matter, making students memorize the countless idioms for examination such as "get under somebody's skin" or "play hooky" is impractical in real communicative situations because these idioms are not generally understood by most people in the international settings. On the contrary, students should be encouraged to spend their time practicing the most frequently used words, which are normally understood by both native and nonnative speakers, in real communication and test them accordingly. Another important point, Thai language planning and policy lacks the basis of scientific data on sociolinguistics. Despite having supported by funds, the language planning and policy are still in grave situation as all decisions are relied heavily on the political power as well as bureaucrats' personal opinions. Thus, the current English teaching situation in Thailand, it is necessary to consider the English status and put it into the educational planning and policy as well so that it will be in harmony with new global trends that is based on the varieties of English in multicultural communities.

Current trend of teaching paradigm in Thai educational context

Interestingly, despite the significant promotion of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) as the most effective and desirable teaching approach, many studies (Savignon, 1991; Ellis, 1994; Burnaby & Sun, 1989; Saengboon, 2002) have revealed the key problems in line with sociolinguistic reality after the implementation of CLT in Thailand and in Asian countries. That is, CLT approach is invalid and conflicts with pedagogy and Asian educational conditions since most countries in this area emphasize the importance of the product-orientation and rote memorization method in teaching. In Thai pedagogical condition, most Thai teachers satisfy with the traditional teaching method which contradicts with the use of CLT in the actual classroom. They are not demanded to have particular skills in conducting the class apart from only using English language as the main classroom language. The ultimate goal of teaching students is merely focus on requiring students to memorize the grammatical rules, content or even difficult vocabulary. The Grammar-Translation method has long been employed to implement the reading class by allowing students to read texts with translation along with doing exercises with the use of Thai language (Chang, 2011). Hence, the use of such method is the enormous hinderance of having satisfactorily applied CLT approach in the real classroom. If the teaching paradigm in Thailand is not reexamined and changed, it is virtually impossible to improve student's communicative competence successfully.

Consequently, the implementation of CLT approach based on the paradigm shift from English as a Foreign Language (EFL) to English as an International Language (EIL) should be reconsidered and needs to be improved at different levels of Thai educational setting. The English language teaching paradigm should be revised according to the socio-cultural reality in line with the diverse communicative situations in order to highlight the significance of international intelligibility among global users of English (Baker, 2012). Together, the concept of one-size-fit-all English of the original use of any so-called native speakers is no longer practical as the key to promote the mutual understanding in all communicative situations, especially between people across diverse nations.

Therefore, English language teaching within the new paradigms of Teaching English as an International Language (TEIL) and WEs, should be established and promoted in Thai educational context. To clarify, teachers should conduct their own pedagogical implications for regional multilingualism (Corbett, 2003). They are supposed to potentially accommodate this world language in the classroom with their teaching styles and strategies so that English can serve local communicative needs as well as promote local indigenous languages and cultures. Students should have been equipped with the knowledge of how deal with many varieties of Englishes. The sociolinguistic reality of the current world communication, together with global intelligibility and diversity should be presented in learning materials rather than merely reserving the one ideal standard use of English. The new teaching paradigm should be highlighted the fact that the ultimate goal of learning English is to prepare students for their communicative competence and fostering their ability in using English in the real world's communication (Jenkins, 2006). As a result, in terms of sociolinguistic value, NNESTs are able to have their positive, realistic contribution to the learners' future use of English within diverse communities. In other words, they play a significant role in ELT. For example, in the ASEAN region, non-native teachers have contributed to the advancement of English through their training, experience, and dedication. The dominant English language teaching paradigm in Thailand should be implemented compatibly with globally communicative needs which focus on intercultural communicative competence rather than just follow the conventional norms of the native speaker.

Conclusion

The discussion of this paper could be regarded as the fundamental information and hopeful indicator to encourage all non-native teachers of English to believe in their own strength points in teaching practices. Together, the awareness of students' attitudes towards both NESTs and NNESTs can give the right direction for becoming a more efficient English language teacher in accordance with students' need in the new global trends of English language education that is based on the varieties of English in multicultural communities. With respect to paradigm shift in ELT in Thailand, the new effective teaching approach and selection of material and activities should creatively enable students to truly communicate and gain more intercultural communicative competence without national boundaries. In conclusion, English language education in Thailand needs a new paradigm of EIL instead of implementing the traditional EFL paradigm as the main method which merely promotes the discourse of the native speaker norms. Particularly, the global communicative needs in line with intercultural communicative competence rather than just follow the conventional model of communicative competence should be given the real power. Hopefully, Thai users of English, most recently, will be encouraged to use English to master mutual intelligibility without only clinging on using English due to the ownership of native speakers and be proficient multilingual speakers and possess their communicative repertoires rather than being devaluated as second language (L2) speakers by the norms of native speakers (Widdowson, 1994).

Recommendations

It is recommended that this study can be replicated in other EFL and ESL countries. In addition, new research can be conducted on the effect of current trend of ELT on EFL students' learning English in Thai educational context.

Delimitation

This study is limited to Thai EFL educational context.

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